

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF YORÙBÁ PERSONAL NAME DERIVATION: A PLUTOCRATIC PERSPECTIVE

RIDWAN AKINKUNMI RABIU

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages,

Kwara State University, Malete

Email: ridwan.rabiu@kwasu.edu.ng

Phone Number: +2349060070668

ORCID: 0009-0003-6509-2437

And

IDRIS OLAMIDE EMIOLA

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages,

Kwara State University, Malete

Email: emiolaolamide14@gmail.com

Phone Number +2348078121364

ORCID: 0009-0000-1810-5511

Abstract

This article examined and analysed the social identity properties of Yorùbá personal names, focusing on selected personal names that show the Yorùbá society as a plutocratic one. This study explored the concept of plutocracy in Yoruba society through a socio-psychological analysis of selected Yoruba names. It adopted a qualitative methodological approach, using purposive sampling to select culturally relevant Yorùbá personal names for analysis. Relevant Yorùbá name-data were gathered through a triangulation method which involves interviews, focus group discussions, and extraction of name-data from relevant published texts on Yorùbá names. The analysis is guided by the Social Identity Theory propounded by Tajfel and Turner (1979). Our major findings showed that Yoruba linguistic expressions, most especially Yorùbá names often reflect and reinforce plutocratic values, emphasizing wealth, status, and social mobility as core aspects of personal and collective identities. Through the lens of Yorùbá personal names, it was discovered that the wealthy are classified as the in-group in Yorùbá society and are given royal, cultural and political responsibilities while the low class and the poor people of the society are the out-group who no matter the level of their wisdom and intelligence can only be seen and not heard. In conclusion, these researchers established from the name-data gathered and analyse that names, most especially personal ones are mirror through which the social constructions such as social categorization, social identification and social comparison of a society can be ascertained.

Key Words: Anthroponomastic; Yorùbá; Social Identity; In-group; Out-group

Introduction

Language is a powerful tool through which societies express, preserve, and transmit values. In Yoruba culture, this is evident in the way personal names are used to communicate ideas about wealth, status, and power. Over time, scholars have explored how these linguistic forms reflect the deep-rooted social structures of the Yoruba people. This research provides insight into the cultural significance of names, particularly in relation to how they mirror a society where wealth determines influence and identity.

The Yoruba society, known for its rich cultural heritage, has been undergoing significant transformations in recent times. Despite its traditional democratic and equality values, some scholars argue that plutocratic tendencies have emerged, where wealth and social status increasingly influence power dynamics. However, there is a dearth of research examining how these shifts are reflected in the language and symbolism of Yoruba culture, most especially using Yorùbá name-data as instrument of analysis. This study aims to investigate how selected Yoruba personal names reinforce or challenge plutocratic values, using a socio-plutocratic analysis to uncover the underlying power structures and social commentary embedded in these linguistic and cultural elements.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The Yorùbá naming system is a deeply symbolic and culturally embedded tradition that reflects the values, spirituality, and social structures of the people. Names are more than mere labels; they are narratives that encapsulate birth circumstances, familial hopes, ancestral ties, or even spiritual insights.

Fitzpatrick (2012, p. 29) provides a detailed account of the naming practices among the Yoruba people, emphasizing the cultural importance of naming ceremonies. Fitzpatrick (2012) presents Yoruba naming as a deeply symbolic and communal tradition, rooted in spirituality, family heritage, and cultural values.

Ajiboye (2011) explores the gender distinctions found in Yoruba names and argues that these distinctions are better understood through morphological and sociolinguistic analysis rather than relying solely on semantics. The study examines different types of Yoruba names, including attributive names (orúkọ àmúyẹ), personal names (orúkọ àbísọ), and nicknames (orúkọ ìnagijẹ), and shows that many of these names clearly reflect gender-based meanings. Ajiboye observes that certain names are exclusively given to males because they contain elements such as baba

(father), akín (valour), ogun (war), já (fight), and fẹ́ (to like/love in a strong sense). These names emphasize strength, bravery, and action—qualities culturally assigned to men in Yoruba society. In contrast, names given to females often include words like iyá or iyèyè (mother), ẹwà (beauty), kẹ́ (to adorn), and bẹ́ (to beg), which reflect care, beauty, and emotional appeal. These features, Ajiboye notes, align with traditional roles and values expected of women in the society.

According to Akinola (2014), “Yoruba names serve more than just personal identification; they perform several communicative and socio-cultural roles that reflect the values and worldview of the Yoruba people”.

Oladeji et al. (2022) investigate specific category of Yoruba names derived from proverbs that evolved from appellations to personal names. These names, although they started as expressions on vehicles or buildings, eventually became personal identifiers. The study uses a combination of data from convocation brochures across four universities in southwest Nigeria and oral interviews, offering valuable insight into how proverbs reflect the beliefs, aspirations, and worldview of the Yoruba people. Oladeji’s work is grounded in cultural theory, which supports the idea that these names are more than just identifiers; they are vehicles of Yoruba cultural philosophy.

Adeniyi (2017) categorizes Yoruba names based on the cultural, spiritual, and social values of the Yoruba people. The study explains that Yoruba names are meaningful and reflect important aspects of the child’s birth, family background, and the community’s beliefs.

Olusola (2023) examines the significance of naming in Yoruba culture, highlighting it as a deeply rooted tradition that has been practiced with great care and intention from ancient times. In Yoruba society, names are not randomly chosen; they are often inspired by the circumstances surrounding a child’s conception or birth, and they usually reflect the family’s hopes and aspirations for the child’s future. This is because there is a strong cultural belief that a person’s name has the power to influence their destiny.

Olusola (2023) adopts the Sociology of Literature as the theoretical framework, the study analysed how naming practices among the Yoruba have evolved over time. It draws attention to the contrast between traditional naming customs and the more modern approaches observed in contemporary society. Olusola argues that while naming continues to be important, many of the customs and rituals associated with it in the past have either faded away or changed significantly.

Okota (2025) addresses the relatively underexplored morphophonemic features of indigenous Yoruba polysyllabic names, emphasizing their cultural and linguistic significance. While the broader field of naming practices has received substantial

attention both globally and within Nigeria, the specific morphophonemic processes inherent in Yoruba names have not been thoroughly examined. This gap in the literature limits a comprehensive understanding of how Yoruba names function within both the language system and cultural context.

Okota (2025) research adopts a mixed-method approach within a descriptive research design and is theoretically anchored in Lexical Phonology (LP). A purposive sample of 50 Yoruba names was drawn from first-year Yoruba-major students at Obafemi Awolowo University and the University of Lagos. Over a four-week period, data were collected using structured Google Forms designed to elicit authentic naming data. The analysis focused on identifying the presence of morphological processes, such as affixation, and phonological processes, such as deletion.

The research findings of Okota (2025) research revealed that affixation is the most prevalent morphological process, followed by clipping and compounding. In terms of phonology, vowel harmony emerged as a dominant feature, contributing to fluency and aesthetic appeal in pronunciation. Deletion processes were also observed often employed to simplify complex phonetic structures in Yoruba. The study concludes that Yoruba polysyllabic names exhibit rich morphophonemic characteristics, shaped by the interplay of various linguistic elements. From the works on naming studied so far, it has been established that research in Yorùbá names and naming system has been studied from different perspectives using different theories but few studies have examine Yorùbá names from plutocratic perspective, this is the focus of this research.

Empirical Review

Plutocracy is a system of government where wealth is the sole determinant factor in choosing who controls the society. Nurudeen et al. (2017) describe plutocracy as a “system of government where the wealthy exert significant influence over the political process”. According to Babatunde (2019), a plutocracy is “marked by a system where wealth determines political power. Individuals or groups with substantial financial resources often dominate policy-making and national decision processes.” In such systems, wealthy elites influence governance through campaign financing, lobbying, or even direct control of political institutions.

Babatunde (2019) further argues that “plutocracies typically foster deep social and economic inequalities, with a wide gap between the affluent ruling class and the broader population. Democratic principles may also be compromised, as financial influence reduces transparency and weakens public accountability.” He further provides examples such as the Gilded Age in the United States, when industrialists and financiers had immense sway over political affairs, and post-Soviet Russia, where oligarchs wielded considerable political and economic control. Ojukwu and

Nwaorgu (2020) posit that “plutocracy was classically viewed as a form of oligarchy-government by a wealthy few. In contemporary usage, however, the term describes two related but distinct concepts.”

Johnson (2017) offers a theoretical framework by attributing the sustenance of plutocracy to dominant ideologies. He argues that beliefs such as neoliberalism and social Darwinism play a critical role in maintaining elite rule by normalizing inequality and deregulation. Through media, education, and public discourse, these ideologies are internalized by the masses, making plutocratic rule appear natural or even desirable.

Collectively, these studies demonstrate that plutocracy is not merely a form of government but a pervasive societal phenomenon. It operates across different institutions and is often sustained by ideological mechanisms that obscure its presence. Understanding these perspectives is essential to critically engaging with the structural inequalities embedded in both political and economic systems around the world. The focus of this research is to examine the overt elevation and promotion of plutocracy in Yorùbá society through Yorùbá name derivation.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts Social Identity Theory (Tajfel& Turner, 1979). Social Identity Theory, proposed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner. These scholars posit that individuals derive a sense of identity and self-worth based on their membership in social groups. This theory is instrumental in understanding how names among the Yorùbá people serve not just as linguistic expressions but as markers of group belonging, class consciousness, and social hierarchy. Within a plutocratic context, names can signify lineage, wealth, or status. By applying Social Identity Theory, the study investigates how language becomes a medium for constructing and expressing social roles and collective identities. The adoption of this theory fits into the stratification of people into different social categories and class. The key concepts of social identity theory are social categorization, social identification and social comparison. (Khadka 2023) defines social comparison as:

How individual evaluates their in-group relative to out-group to maintain or enhance self-esteem. Positive comparison where the in-group is perceived as superior often lead to in-group favouritism and out-group biases.

This theory is instrumental in understanding how personal names among the Yorùbá people serve not just as linguistic expressions but as markers of group belonging, class consciousness, and social hierarchy. Within a plutocratic context personal names often articulate shared values or societal expectations that reinforce social boundaries. By applying Social Identity Theory, this study investigates how

language becomes a medium for constructing and expressing social roles and collective identities. These, the researchers observed that while the Social Identity Theory have been used to analyse different salient topics in politics and governance, public administration, religion, gender studies etc. While research works on Yorùbá name and naming system, little or no research work to the best of these researchers knowledge have examine and analyse how Yorùbá personal names are used to classify people into the in-group and out-group, most especially using the Social Identity Theory. This is the vacuum this research work aim to fill.

Research Methodology

In line with the qualitative research design, this study employs multiple data collection methods to gather rich, detailed information on Yoruba names. According to Patton (2002), qualitative data collection techniques such as interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis are effective in capturing participants' life experiences and cultural meanings. Specifically, primary data will be collected via previous literatures and archives of Yoruba names relating to the concept of study.

Additionally, data will be sourced from literary texts, cultural archives, and existing compilations of Yoruba names, as recommended by Creswell (2014), to triangulate and enrich the data. This multi-source approach enhances the validity of findings by providing a comprehensive perspective on the socio-syntactic features under investigation.

The population for this research includes Yorùbá names that are widely used across south-western Nigeria, particularly in traditional and socio-political settings. The sample comprises a purposively selected list of twenty Yorùbá names. These were chosen based on their frequency of usage, semantic richness, and relevance to the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

SN	Personal Name	Meaning	Social Identity Analysis
i.	Olówólayémò	The world only knows and recognize the wealthy	This name reflects in-group visibility. The rich and wealthy people are remembered, praised, and referenced, while the poor (out-group) are forgotten, reinforcing the idea that identity is tied to wealth.
ii.	Olówòdkéré	A wealthy person is not small.	This presents the wealthy as emotionally stable and noble (in-group), while the poor are viewed as bitter or lacking grace

			(out-group), creating a moral class divide.
iii.	Owónifáàrí	Money brings prestige.	Prestige and respect are reserved for the wealthy in-group. The poor are deprived of admiration, making economic status the gatekeeper of social pride.
iv.	Owóadé	Wealth is the crown.	Leadership and honour are now wealth-based. Those with money belong to the ruling in-group, while others are excluded from authority.
v.	Owóṣééńí	Wealth is available for everyone.	This name suggests that money is the most desirable possession not just useful but essential. In a Yoruba plutocratic society, such a name reinforces the idea that being part of the wealthy in-group is both ideal and necessary. Under Social Identity Theory, identity and self-worth are tied to group membership, and here, being wealthy becomes the ticket into the respected group. The poor are, by implication, not just disadvantaged but socially misplaced, as they lack the very thing that defines value and belonging.
vi.	Owólafé	It is money we desire.	This name reflects a collective orientation toward wealth, showing how deeply money shapes both individual and communal identity in Yoruba society. From the perspective of Social Identity Theory, this desire defines the boundary between the in-group (the wealthy) and the out-group (the poor). Desiring money implies aspiring to belong to the dominant class, where prestige, voice, and influence reside. It also reveals how society has come to equate value, respect, and even moral worth with economic status. Those who lack wealth are not just excluded, they are seen as failing to reach the standard of desirability. This

			reinforces group discrimination, as the poor become the marginalized “others” whose voices and identities carry less social weight.
vii.	Owóyèlé	Money befits a home.	Using Social Identity Theory, this name positions wealthy families as the in-group. The admired, respected, and seen as models of success. Poor homes, by contrast, are not only deprived materially but are socially framed as incomplete, unattractive, or unworthy. This fosters class based identity bias, where group membership is determined by economic condition, and dignity is distributed unevenly based on material possessions. The value of the family, therefore, is no longer intrinsic, but defined by the wealth it displays. Within a family, the rich is extolled and celebrated while the poor is denigrated and ostracized.
viii.	Olówòṣèlú	The wealthy governs the town.	This name expresses the belief that political leadership and social authority are no longer tied to lineage, wisdom, tradition or capacity but to wealth. It asserts that economic power now determines who leads, whose voice is heard, and whose decisions matter. Using Social Identity Theory, this name defines the wealthy as the in-group, those who shape the society and are recognized as legitimate rulers. The poor form the out-group, often side-lined from leadership and decision-making spaces. This name reinforces the plutocratic structure of Yoruba society, where governance and influence are reserved for the economically privileged. It shapes identity by linking leadership potential to class identity and not the merit and audacity of individuals aspiring for a

			position of authority, thereby excluding a large segment of the society from meaningful participation.
Ix	Olówósayé	The wealthy rules the world.	This name suggests that true enjoyment, peace, and the fullness of life are exclusive privileges of the rich. In a Yorùbá society influenced by plutocratic values, it reinforces the idea that wealth is the gateway to happiness, comfort, and respect. According to Social Identity Theory, this creates a distinct social divide: the wealthy become the desirable in-group who are seen as successful, joyful, and enviable, while the poor are relegated to the out-group perceived as suffering, incomplete, and unfortunate. The name does not just describe reality; it helps construct it, embedding the idea that meaningful life is inaccessible without money. This marginalizes the poor both materially and socially, defining their identity as one of lack and exclusion.
x.	Olówójoyè	The rich is given chieftaincy titles.	This name reflects the commercialization of honour in Yorùbá society, where chieftaincy titles, once earned through age, wisdom, or service to humanity and community are now conferred based on wealth. It underscores the shift from meritocracy to plutocracy, where money has become the main qualification for cultural recognition. Through the lens of Social Identity Theory, this name reinforces the privileged position of the rich as the in-group, who not only control resources but also receive societal validation and status. The poor, in contrast, form the out-group, excluded from traditional honours regardless of their integrity or contribution to the

			society. Thus, identity and respect become financially determined, and prestige is reserved for those who can afford it, deepening class-based divisions. Social recognition can now be described as a situation where the rich buy and sell and the poor can only window-shop.
xi.	Olówóládé	The wealthy owns royalty.	This name makes a symbolic and literal equation between wealth and royalty. It implies that in contemporary Yorùbá society, financial power has overtaken traditional criteria like noble lineage or moral standing as the source of authority and prestige. Using Social Identity Theory, this naming expression marks the rich as the in-group that holds both cultural and symbolic power, equivalent to that of a crown. This creates an identity boundary where the poor are not only materially disadvantaged but also denied symbolic relevance. Their exclusion from such powerful labels keeps them outside the circle of influence, as identity in a plutocratic system is closely tied to what one possesses, not who one is. The name thus reinforces the idea that wealth crowns a person with social, political, and cultural dominance.
xii	Fowósayé	Enjoy life with money	This name promotes the belief that the purpose of wealth is enjoyment and fulfilment. It suggests that those who have money are the ones truly living, while those without it merely exist. From the standpoint of Social Identity Theory, this name solidifies the rich as the in-group, those entitled to happiness, leisure, and satisfaction. The poor become the out-group, symbolizing lack not just of material resources, but of the

			right to joy themselves. This creates an identity gap where wealth is not just a possession but a passport to emotional and social validation. In a plutocratic society, such a name elevates the spender and marginalizes the one who cannot afford to participate in the pleasures of life.
xiii)	Olówólàgbà	The wealthy one is the superior.	This name boldly affirms class based superiority by equating wealth with higher status. It expresses a social identity where the rich are perceived as inherently better, wiser, or more respectable simply because of their material possessions. From the lens of Social Identity Theory, this name solidifies the wealthy as the dominant in-group whose social category is associated with power and influence. The poor, by contrast, become the marginalized out-group defined by lack and inferiority. Such a name reinforces social hierarchies and encourages identity formation based on class distinction, validating the dominance of the rich while deepening the alienation of the poor.
xiv)	Oláowó	If not for money	This name reflects a worldview where money is central to all decisions, behaviours, and social outcomes. It suggests that economic considerations outweigh moral or emotional ones, and people are judged based on financial capability. From the perspective of Social Identity Theory, this reinforces group membership and worth based on material status. The rich are portrayed as purposeful and respected because money defines their path, while the poor are relegated to the out-group whose choices are invalidated by lack of resources. This strengthens the notion that success and social identity are inseparable from wealth.

xv)	Olówóòfóyèkú	The rich does not lack chieftaincy titles	<p>This name emphasizes that money is the most important element in life, overshadowing other values such as character, wisdom, or spirituality. It promotes the idea that financial power is the key to influence, respect, and achievement. Viewed through the Social Identity Theory, the name positions the rich as the central and celebrated in-group in society. They are the individuals whose opinions matter, whose lifestyles are envied, and whose identities are idealized. Conversely, the poor are pushed into the out-group, portrayed as irrelevant or unsuccessful due to their lack of the one thing that truly counts which is money. This naming ideology affirms a plutocratic society where wealth defines all metrics of identity and belonging.</p>
xvi)	Owónikókó	Money is the main thing	<p>This name emphasizes that money is the most important element in life, overshadowing other values such as character, wisdom, moral, values or spirituality. It promotes the idea that financial power is the key to influence, respect, and achievement. Viewed through the Social Identity Theory, the name positions the rich as the central and celebrated in-group in society. They are the individuals whose opinions matter, whose lifestyles are envied, and whose</p>

			<p>identities are idealized. Conversely, the poor are pushed into the out-group, portrayed as irrelevant or unsuccessful due to their lack of the one thing that truly counts which is money. This naming ideology affirms a plutocratic society where wealth defines all metrics of identity and belonging. This name shows that money, and not knowledge is the most important factor in human society.</p>
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xvii)	Adéfowórà	The crown is bought with money.	<p>This name reflects a powerful shift in cultural values where money, rather than tradition or virtue, becomes the pathway to power. It suggests that even the most sacred institutions, like kingship or leadership, can now be accessed through wealth. Social Identity Theory helps us understand how this name elevates the rich to the role of political and cultural gatekeepers, forming an exclusive in-group. It challenges traditional norms and places economic capital as the determinant of identity and access. Those without money are excluded from leadership roles and stripped of influence, reinforcing their identity as the disadvantaged out-group.</p>
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xviii)	Adéfolarin	Royalty Walks in Wealth	This name blends nobility with material affluence, suggesting that royalty without wealth is incomplete. It implies that traditional titles and honours now require financial backing to retain their prestige. From the viewpoint of Social Identity Theory, the name reinforces an in-group of elites who hold both noble and economic capital. It excludes those who may possess one but lack the other, especially the poor, who are unable to align themselves with either domains. In this context, the name underscores a society where wealth must accompany honour for one's identity to be fully validated. This shows that in contemporary Yorùbá society, wealth and royalty are an inseparable siamese twin
xix)	Owógboyè	Money earns title	This name reflects the growing perception in a plutocratic Yoruba society that titles and honours are no longer based on merit, lineage, or service but can be acquired through wealth. It implies that with enough money, societal recognition becomes accessible to anyone. Through the lens of Social Identity Theory, this reinforces a class-based in-group, those with the financial means to claim identity, respect, and leadership. The poor, on the other hand, are cast into the out-group, who are denied symbolic value because they lack economic power. This naming ideology emphasizes that in the social hierarchy, money does not just buy things, it buys identity and prestige.

xx)	Olágboyè	Wealth earns titles	This name reinforces the idea that social titles and honours in Yorùbá society are awarded based on material wealth rather than personal achievement or inherited status. It reflects a cultural shift where recognition is commoditized, accessible primarily to those with economic power. From the Social Identity Theory perspective, this positions the wealthy as the dominant in-group whose financial capability secures them elevated social identities. The poor, by contrast, become the out-group excluded from systems of honour and influence. In this structure, identity is tied to what one owns, not who one is, intensifying class boundaries and reinforcing the values of a plutocratic society.
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Findings

Through this research it was discovered that Yoruba names mirrors the society and revealed the social stratification where people are classified into the in-group and out-group social classes. Examples of such names are “Olówólayémò” which means ‘the world only knows and recognizes the wealthy’, “Olówólàgbà” which means ‘the wealthy one is the superior’, and “Olówóòfóyèkù” which means ‘the rich does not lack chieftaincy titles’ etc. are not merely personal identifiers but indicators of class identity which class the rich and wealthy as the in-group and the poor as the out-group. These selected Yorùbá names construct an in-group identity for the rich and place the poor in the out-group. Fakuade et al. (2018) give credence to this assertion when they opine that “personal names strongly reveal the power of names to emphasize social relationships. Personal names are iconic representations of composite social variable”.

Plutocracy as a cultural logic shows the consistent reference to wealth as a measure of power and privilege indicates that Yoruba society now operates under a plutocratic logic. Social Identity Theory SIT successfully explained how language, in this case, Yorùbá names are used to maintain class distinction, allowing the rich to claim superiority and visibility while dictating to the poor subtly through names that they are not to be seen or heard.

Conclusion

This study has shown that Yorùbá language practices, particularly, naming plays a central role in constructing and preserving class-based identities. Wealth is not only a means of survival but has become the basis for social ranking, moral judgment, and even spiritual worth. The language used to describe people and their value in society reflects and reinforces a plutocratic structure. This implies that identity in Yorùbá culture is now tightly bound to economic standing, marginalizing those without wealth and privileging the rich as the societal standard.

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